

Teacher absenteeism: a conceptual model developed from a systematic literature review

Laura María García Carrizosa ¹, Kristof De Witte^{2,3}

1. Faculty of Economics and Business, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Spain.
2. Leuven Economics of Education Research, Faculty of Economics and Business, KU Leuven, Belgium.
3. Maastricht University, The Netherlands.

Summary

1. This brief summarizes a systematic review of 89 studies analyzing teacher absenteeism and its contributing factors.
2. A conceptual model was developed, identifying 40 key variables that influence teacher absenteeism across individual, school, work, and environmental contexts.
3. The analysis highlights significant correlates of absenteeism and reveals diverse approaches to addressing the issue.
4. Teacher absenteeism is shown to negatively impact student achievement, underscoring its broader educational consequences.
5. Policy recommendations focus on improving teacher well-being, enhancing working conditions, and establishing comprehensive monitoring and accountability systems for attendance.

1. Introduction

Teacher absenteeism impacts the quality and continuity of education, leading to significant costs at both individual and societal levels. The costs originate from lost productivity, additional payments to cover absent teachers, and administrative expenses for managing absences. Besides these financial burdens, teacher absenteeism disrupts students' learning, diminishes student motivation, and stimulates a negative perception of teachers

among students and parents (Green, 2014). Frequent teacher absenteeism could impede educational progress and create substantial learning deficits (Gambi & De Witte, 2023), which have long-term repercussions for individuals and society.

This policy brief summarizes a systematic literature review of factors linked to teacher absenteeism and the predictors associated with taking time off work. In addition, a conceptual model of the predictors of teacher absenteeism is presented, recognizing the

challenges to mitigating this difficult situation in schools and developing strategies based on evidenced results. As such, this policy brief intends to provide policymakers with proactive plans for preventing absenteeism.

2. Data and Methodology

The research process is conducted in multiple phases, adhering to the guidelines for reporting systematic reviews as recommended by the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) (Page et al., 2021). The search focuses on studies published between 1990 and September 2022, limited to English-language papers in peer-reviewed journals to ensure the relevance and broader applicability of the findings.

The final dataset for this systematic literature review includes 89 papers. These papers primarily investigate the reasons behind teachers' absences from work, with some focusing on the predictors of absenteeism, others on the consequences, and a few on potential solutions to this issue.

3. Results

The systematic review analyzes 89 articles on teacher absenteeism, highlighting a recent surge in publications, reflecting the growing awareness of the impact of teacher attendance on student outcomes and educational quality. The studies span 30 countries, with the United States, Israel, Finland, Indonesia, and Brazil contributing the most research. Across Europe, 15 studies examine teacher absenteeism. Only six articles include data from multiple countries. Cross-country comparisons are challenging due to difficulties in gathering data, differences in measuring absenteeism, and variations in

educational systems. The scope of these studies also varies based on factors such as funding, research capacity, and data collection methods like interviews and surveys.

56 articles use quantitative methods, with most employing descriptive analysis or linear regression to examine the relationship between absenteeism and its predictors. Other common methodologies refer to Poisson/negative binomial, and logistic regressions. Sample sizes vary widely, with most studies based on 500 to 5,000 observations. Only 18 papers employ qualitative analysis to examine teacher absenteeism. These studies focus on identifying the predictors of absenteeism, and their findings are consistent with those of quantitative research.

The review identifies 40 variables associated with teacher absenteeism, which we categorized into four levels, forming a **novel conceptual model** (see Figure 1):

(1) **Teacher factors** (Sociodemographic and psychological), which are micro-level variables that incorporate the individual factors that might be associated with the ability and motivation to attend work.

(2) **Working conditions**, linked to job characteristics that could impact teacher's attendance.

(3) **School characteristics** (organizational factors and physical characteristics), which are macro-level variables that may affect educator's behavior within the school; and

(4) **Environmental factors**, the most general category related to external characteristics that could indirectly influence the motivation to attend to work.

These categories help organize the variables and identify the most common associations. Key predictors of absenteeism include teacher characteristics like gender and age. For example, most studies indicate that women tend to have higher absenteeism rates than men. Additionally, higher job satisfaction and commitment are strongly associated with lower absenteeism. Better working conditions and an improved physical environment promote attendance, while less monitoring and supervision leads to higher absenteeism (Guerrero et al., 2013).

The consequences of absenteeism are primarily linked to a negative impact on student achievement (Benhenda, 2022), with studies showing that ten additional days of teacher absence can reduce student test scores by 1.7% to 3.3% of a standard deviation. Other consequences of teacher nonattendance at work, less investigated but also mentioned in some reviewed articles, are related to poorer student attendance, higher student dropout rates, and more conflict among teachers (Gørtz & Andersson, 2014). However, there is limited discussion on how absenteeism affects teachers themselves, such as its impact on their teaching, professional growth, or long-term career commitment.

4. Policy Recommendations

The literature review highlights several key policy implications for effectively addressing teacher absenteeism. Clearly, there is no magic formula or a single solution to disentangle the complex phenomenon of absenteeism in the education sector. Isolated interventions hardly ever work. Nevertheless, diverse initiatives tackling the different levels of predictors of teacher absenteeism could be effective. The developed conceptual model helps us recall that policies must incorporate

coordinated actions at individual, school, and work levels.

First, it is crucial to prioritize teachers' physical and emotional well-being by implementing initiatives that promote health, enhance job satisfaction, and reduce stress and anxiety. Additionally, helping teachers balance their personal, family, and work responsibilities is essential for managing their professional and personal lives effectively.

Second, schools should improve working conditions by ensuring fair workloads, providing autonomy, recognition, and proper contract terms. Creating a positive work environment, offering non-monetary incentives, and providing supportive leadership are also important for boosting teacher morale and reducing absenteeism.

Improving the accuracy of administrative records on teacher attendance is essential. Establishing formal systems for reporting absences, ensuring educational continuity, and preventing teacher shortages are critical steps. At the system level, targeted policies and regulations are necessary, including disciplinary measures to deter absenteeism and robust monitoring systems to maintain the integrity of attendance records. Community involvement is also important, with communities supporting efforts to improve teacher attendance, often facilitated by Parent-Teacher Associations (PTAs), which serve as key channels for collaboration.

Moreover, disparities in teacher absenteeism across different socio-economic contexts require tailored interventions, especially for low-income schools. Given the impact of resource limitations and poor environmental conditions on teacher health, targeted efforts are needed to address the specific challenges faced by disadvantaged schools. Coordinated

initiatives that are aligned with specific educational contexts are essential for effectively reducing absenteeism, emphasizing the need for a comprehensive and multifaceted approach to intervention strategies.

What is EFFEct ?

EFFEct is an impact-driven research project aiming to enhance the quality of education in the EU by providing evidence-based policy recommendations and conducting rigorous research on the education policies of individual EU member states.

References

- Benhenda, A. (2022). Absence, substitutability and productivity: Evidence from teachers. *Labour Economics*, 76, 102167.
- Gambi, L. & De Witte, K. (2023). The uphill battle: The amplifying effects of negative trends in test scores, COVID-19 school closures and teacher shortages (Working paper). KU Leuven
- Gørtz, M., & Andersson, E. (2014). Child-to-teacher ratio and day care teacher sickness absenteeism. *Health economics*, 23(12), 1430–1442.
- Green, G. (2014). Study to investigate self-reported teacher absenteeism and desire to leave teaching as they relate to teacher-reported teaching satisfaction, job-related stress, symptoms of depression, irrational beliefs and self-efficacy. [Doctoral dissertation, University of New York]. CUNY Academic Works.
- Guerrero, G., León, J., Zapata, M., & Cueto, S. (2013). Getting teachers back to the classroom. A systematic review on what works to improve teacher attendance in developing countries. *Journal of Development Effectiveness*, 5(4), 466–488.
- Page, M. J., McKenzie, J. E., Bossuyt, P. M., Boutron, I., Hoffmann, T. C., Mulrow, C. D., Shamseer, L., Tetzlaff, J. M., Akl, E. A., Brennan, S. E., Chou, R., Glanville, J., Grimshaw, J. M., Hróbjartsson, A., Lalu, M. M., Li, T., Loder, E. W., Mayo-Wilson, E., McDonald, S., ...Moher, D. (2021). The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ*, 372(71).

Figure 1. Conceptual model predictors of teacher absenteeism

*Note: The numbers in brackets represent the number of reviewed articles in which the variable has been included.

Further Information:

García Carrizosa, L.M & De Witte, K. (2024). Teacher absenteeism: a conceptual model developed from a systematic literature review. *Cambridge Journal of Education*. DOI: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/0305764X.2024.2397366?scroll=top&needAccess=true>.

EFFEct is funded by the European Commission in its Horizon Europe framework (grant 101129146). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the granting authority. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Follow us online www.effect-project.eu

Follow us on X @EFFEct_Proj

Follow us on LinkedIn www.linkedin.com/company/EFFEct-project/